

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR AN INCREASED SUPPORT OF CITIZEN SCIENCE IN POLAND

The **European Citizen Science (ECS)**¹ project, funded by the European Union, aims to expand and strengthen the citizen science (CS) community in Europe through training and awareness-raising activities. Its advocacy goal is to promote the recognition of CS as a powerful tool to support policymaking and a valuable research approach for scientific excellence and sustainable development across Europe.

As part of the project, a series of national events were held with the goal of co-creating policy recommendations to enhance and embed CS into national schemes within EU Member States. On **June 10th, 2025**, the **Institute of Urban and Regional Development** organized the event **"Współtworzenie zmian: nauka obywatelska, polityka krajowa, oddziaływanie"** (from the English **"Co-creating change: citizen science, national policy, impact"**) in Kraków, Poland. It brought together key stakeholders from across the quadruple helix (4H) (academy, industry, policymakers and citizens) to reflect on the development of CS at the national level and co-create policy recommendations to strengthen its role within the Polish research and innovation ecosystem.

Participants included **Monika Szewczyk** and **Bartłomiej Sroka** from the Institute of Urban and Regional Development, **Monika Perek-Jura**, Head of Public Relations and Cooperation with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) at the Nowosolna Municipal Office and member of the **Łódź Cała Naprzód!** association, and **Michał Rzeźnik** from the Koluszki Town and Municipality Office. The private sector was represented by **Marcin Danielewicz** from Watmar and **Tadeusz Marciniak** from BI-Management.

The event fostered constructive dialogue among all participants, who worked collaboratively to identify current challenges and propose actionable steps to promote CS in Poland. Overall, participants emphasized the need for tailored capacity-building, dedicated support structures, legal reinforcement of participatory practices, and stronger recognition and feedback mechanisms to ensure the long-term relevance and impact of CS across sectors.

We want to thank all participants for their valuable contributions and input in shaping this policy brief.

WHAT IS CITIZEN SCIENCE?

As defined by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA): CS, in general, means the participation of the public in science and research. It is an open and inclusive approach, with key characteristics including: (1) citizens are actively involved in research; and (2) there is a genuine science outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change².

¹ <https://eu-citizen.science/>

² <https://www.ecsa.ngo/10-principles/>

CS contributes actively to the democratization of scientific research by increasing public awareness of societal challenges, such as climate change, urban development strategies or biodiversity conservation, promoting trust in science and, scientific literacy, while fostering critical thinking and behavioural change. Involving society in research allows for the collection of larger volumes of data, by those who often are the most affected and that at the same time could benefit from, making information more accessible and relevant to real-world needs. This approach amplifies diverse voices and ensures that research reflects the concerns of all community members.

METHODOLOGY

The main objective of the event was to co-create policy recommendations tailored to Poland's research and innovation (R&I) context for enhanced support of CS. The event was divided into a theoretical framework presentation and the implementation of a co-creation process focused on understanding 4-H stakeholders' **motivations** for engaging with CS, identifying **challenges**, and developing actionable policy **solutions**.

The methodology used hereby is based on one the those used in the Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) on Citizen Science led by the European Commission³, following a backcasting planning approach based on an A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step Framework, starting with defining future goals (A - Aims & Vision) and working backwards to identify practical steps (C- Creative Solutions and D- Decide on Priorities) towards achieving them based on the country's baseline (B- Baseline Analysis). Both the future goals and the baseline analysis were provided during the theoretical part of the event.

Fig 1. Backcasting in the MLE, following the A-B-C-D method developed by The Natural Step

³ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Gold, M., Arias, R., Haklay, M., Irwin, A. et al., Mutual learning exercise – Citizen science initiatives – Policy and practice – Final report, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/988919>

THE CASE OF POLAND

Poland has a growing (CS) ecosystem, with roots that trace back to the 19th century through early public participation in scientific activities. In its more modern and organized form, CS in Poland began to take shape in the early 2000s (mainly focused on the field of the natural sciences) with accelerated development after Poland's accession to the EU in 2004, thanks to structural funds.

Among the initiatives that have emerged over the years, it can be highlighted the BioBlitz programme⁴ (2008) for recording biodiversity; marine environment projects led by the Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (2011), and EDU-ARCTIC⁵ (2016), which promoted Arctic research among young people.

In the following years, CS gained greater visibility within academic and research communities, especially through international grant participation. Notable recent examples include JoinUs4Health (2023)⁶, which involved citizens in cohort studies on public health, and CREST (2025)⁷, aimed at fostering cross-sector cooperation with societal involvement.

Institutionally, CS in Poland is mainly driven by research institutes, universities and NGOs. These actors often engage in CS through grassroots initiatives or in response to international opportunities, particularly within Horizon Europe. While CS is gaining traction, it still lacks strong institutional embedding in the national regulatory framework.

From a policy perspective, CS is referenced in the *State Science Policy*⁸ adopted in 2022, where it is highlighted as the third pillar of open science, alongside open access to publications and research data. Elements related to CS are also indirectly supported through the *Law on Higher Education and Science*⁹, which introduces terms such as “social responsibility of science” and “dissemination of science.” Nonetheless, CS is not explicitly defined or systematically integrated across legislation, evaluation systems, or national strategies.

⁴ https://www.iopan.gda.pl/bio_blitz/bioblitz.html

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/710240/pl>

⁶ <https://joinus4health.eu/citizen-science-week-2023-healthy-cities-summary/>

⁷ <https://crestproject.eu>

⁸ <https://www.gov.pl/web/nauka/polityka-naukowa-panstwa-przyjeta-przez-rade-ministrow> (original in Polish)

⁹ <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20180001668/U/D20181668Lj.pdf> (original in Polish)

THE CASE OF POLAND

Regarding funding, CS projects can access limited national support through calls from agencies such as the NCN¹⁰ (under the Humanities and Social Sciences panel), the NCBR¹¹ (social innovation calls), and ministerial programmes focused on environmental and climate challenges. However, European funds continue to represent the main source of financial support for CS in Poland, indicating a strong dependency on international funding mechanisms.

Despite this, Poland has a growing interest in CS methodologies. Moreover, research on CS in the Polish context still requires in-depth analysis and efforts have been made to define the profile of a “Polish citizen scientist.” Similar to broader European trends, they tend to be older, urban-dwelling, highly educated individuals who are socially engaged and often retired or employed¹².

While the CS community in Poland is expanding, systemic challenges persist. These include a lack of stable national funding, insufficient recognition of CS in research evaluation frameworks, and the absence of a central strategy or coordinating institution. However, the combination of EU funding, growing awareness among researchers, and increasing public engagement signals strong potential for long-term development.

During the event, participants identified several key motivations, challenges and proposed solutions that serve as basis for the policy recommendations for enhancing the support of CS within Poland's national framework.

¹⁰ Narodowe Centrum Nauki (National Science Centre) is a government agency, supervised by the Ministry of Education and Science.

¹¹ Narodowe Centrum Badań i Rozwoju (National Centre for Research and Development) is a government agency supporting innovation by funding scientific research and development in Poland.

¹² Gawronska-Nowak, B, Lis, P, Zadorozhna, O & Zarzycka, A 2023, 'Profiling European citizen scientist: Evidence from Poland', *Journal of International Studies*, vol. 16, no.4, pp. 281 - 295.
<https://doi.org/10.14254/2071-8330.2023/16-4/18>.

MOTIVATIONS

Shared Challenges, Shared Solutions

CS fosters knowledge generation that actively involves all stakeholder groups, ensuring it is inclusive and closely connected to local contexts. This collaborative approach enables decision-makers and service providers to co-create solutions that are relevant and effectively address real community needs. By sharing ownership of both the questions and the outcomes, CS strengthens legitimacy and supports more equitable, trusted decision-making processes.

Cross-sector collaboration and mutual learning

CS provides a practical space to bring together actors who do not typically work side by side. It enables partnerships across public, private, academic, and community spheres, encouraging dialogue and the exchange of perspectives. Through this, CS not only drives innovation but also helps build trust and break down institutional silos.

Disseminating Research Beyond Academia

CS offers a unique opportunity to make research results more visible and meaningful to society. By involving non-academic actors in the definition, production, interpretation and dissemination of data, CS helps ensure that findings do not remain confined to scientific circles. Instead, results are communicated in accessible, relatable ways that allow communities, policymakers, and other stakeholders to engage with and act on the knowledge produced.

Raising Awareness of Societal Challenges

CS makes abstract or overlooked issues more tangible through hands-on participation, whether it's biodiversity loss, pollution, or public health risks. By bringing people into direct contact with the problems being studied, CS fosters a deeper understanding of complex challenges and supports a better informed and engaged public. This awareness is crucial for driving behavioral change and building support for evidence-informed solutions.

Environmental Stewardship, Territorial and Societal Resilience

CS is also valued for its potential to support ecological goals and sustainable urban development. It plays a role in monitoring and protecting biodiversity, restoring degraded ecosystems, and rethinking the relationship between people and nature across different territories. By engaging citizens in these processes, CS contributes to stronger, resilient and more adaptive communities.

CHALLENGES

Awareness, Capacity, and Skills

The implementation of CS is often hindered by a lack of both awareness and practical capacity. Many actors are unfamiliar with what CS involves or how to approach it meaningfully. At the same time, public institutions frequently lack the time, trained staff, or methodological know-how to design and support participatory processes. Citizens, too, may feel unprepared to contribute due to scientific complexity or unclear expectations. These gaps create uneven starting points and can result in weak engagement, poorly structured initiatives, and limited long-term impact.

Structural and Regulatory Constraints

Institutional rigid structure, national political parties priorities - sometimes misaligned with local/regional needs - and legal uncertainty present significant obstacles. Public authorities may be limited by administrative procedures or a lack of autonomy, while industry express confusion and concern about data protection regulations like General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). These systemic constraints make it harder to launch or scale-up CS initiatives, especially when collaboration across sectors is needed.

Trust and Power Imbalances

Mistrust between actors continues to undermine participation. Some citizens perceive engagement efforts as tokenistic, while institutions may hesitate to fully integrate non-expert knowledge. In other cases, dominant voices or institutional priorities can overshadow grassroots input. These dynamics reinforce existing power asymmetries, discourage dialogue, and make it difficult to establish the mutual respect and accountability needed for successful CS initiatives. Local communities often want to make decisions but don't have the real power to do so – spatial planning is a critical example where improved community involvement mechanisms are needed.

Recognition and Incentives

Participants often struggle to stay engaged when they don't see clear outcomes from their involvement or don't receive timely feedback. The lack of recognition – whether symbolic or material – can make their contribution feel undervalued, reducing motivation and making it harder to sustain long-term participation. On the other hand, the academic sector calls for incentive structures that reward CS engagement within research evaluation and career assessment frameworks.

SOLUTIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Strengthen Legal and Institutional Frameworks

Stronger legal mandates that embed CS and participatory processes into governance, particularly at the local level, are necessary to make participation a structural component rather than an optional add-on. Guaranteeing greater autonomy for municipalities to design and implement CS initiatives without excessive interference from political party affiliations is essential. Clearer mandates should encourage cross-sector collaboration and consistent investment in participatory approaches.

Establish Citizen Science Support Structures

Spur the creation of **Citizen Science Support Centres** – dedicated hubs that offer hands-on support to all stakeholders. Their role would be to provide technical advice, matchmaking between actors, and help with legal and/or data-related issues. They would also ensure accessibility by addressing linguistic, digital, and physical barriers, and help reduce the bureaucratic burden that often limits participation, especially for companies, smaller organisations or grassroots initiatives.

Tailor Capacity-Building to Stakeholder Needs

Building capacity is key and must be adapted to different actors. Public administrations need training in facilitation and participatory methods. Companies require guidance on how to design CS-compatible processes and manage regulatory aspects. Researchers would benefit from support in trust-building and inclusive communication, while citizens need accessible entry points and opportunities to gain confidence. Introducing CS transversally into formal education should be adopted as a long-term strategy to promote culture change and normalize citizens participation in scientific research processes.

SOLUTIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Foster the Use of Existing Tools and Resources

Promote scalability and efficiency, by using and/or complementing existing resources, tools, methodologies, and datasets. This includes re-using or adapting protocols already developed in other countries or contexts, especially in thematic areas like biodiversity or environmental monitoring. This encourages reducing duplication of effort, lower entry barriers for new initiatives, and accelerates implementation by building on what already works.

Enhance Recognition, Reward, and Feedback

Sustaining engagement in CS requires both timely feedback and visible acknowledgement of contributions. As such, **formal recognition mechanisms** — such as certifications, public acknowledgements, or ranking systems — that validate the time and effort invested by individuals and organisations, **need to be effectively put in place**. Particularly in academia, recognition should be embedded in research evaluation and career assessment frameworks to ensure that CS is valued as a legitimate form of scholarly contribution.

Support Inclusive Communication Strategies

Dissemination of results should not be limited to contributors but extended to wider audiences to raise awareness and foster cross-sector understanding, for example, through national and/or local events. Sharing successful CS initiatives and their tangible outcomes can help build trust, normalize participation, and demonstrate the broader value of citizen-generated knowledge. Additionally, CS requires targeted communication strategies that consider linguistic, digital, cultural, and physical accessibility and would benefit from professional science communicators expertise.

POLICY BRIEF DETAILS

Authors:

Mireia Ros (Science for Change), Arkadiusz Tomaszek (Institute of Urban and Regional Development), Bogna Gawrońska-Nowak (Institute of Urban and Regional Development), Héloïse Vilaseca (Science for Change), Anita Zarzycka (Institute of Urban and Regional Development).

4H contributors to the co-creation activities (publication permission granted only):

Marcin Danielewicz (Watmar), Tadeusz Marciniak (BI-Management), Monika Perek-Jura (Nowosolna Municipal Office, member of the Łódź Cała Naprzód! association), Michał Rzeźnik (Koluszki Town and Municipality Office), Bartłomiej Sroka (Institute of Urban and Regional Development) and Monika Szewczyk (Institute of Urban and Regional Development).

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Reviewed by:

Marine Masson (Science For Change)
Joana Magalhães (Science for Change)